

Synthesis of some New 1,2,4-Triazines containing Aminopyrimidine Moiety

M. SEADA, R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN* and F. HANAFY

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Education, Ain Shams University, Roxy, Cairo, Egypt

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In continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis of heterocyclic systems derived from pyrimidines¹ and the reported biological properties of 1,2,4-triazines^{2,3}, we have incorporated these two heterocyclic moieties via condensation of the title hydrazinopyrimidine with various oxo-compounds. The sequence of these reactions is depicted in Schemes 1 and 2.

Scheme 1

2-Amino-4-hydrazino-6-chloropyrimidine (1) was condensed with acetophenone derivatives in glacial acetic acid to give the hydrazones (2a-c) which underwent addition of HCN in acetic acid-ethanol mixture giving the cyanohydrins (3a-c). Further, acidic hydrolysis of 3a-c by refluxing with concentrated HCl⁴ led to the formation of 6-amino-3-aryl-8-chloro-2H-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazino[4,3-c]pyrimidin-4-ones (4a-c).

Compound 1 was also condensed with 4-aminoantipyrine in absolute ethanol in presence of a few drops of acetic acid to give the hydrazone

(5), which on refluxing with glacial acetic acid-fused sodium acetate via acylation followed by cyclocondensation, produced 2-[2'-amino-6'-chloropyrimidin-4'-yl]-7-phenyl-3,5,6-trimethylpyrazolo[4,3-e][1,2,4]-triazine (6).

A similar condensation of compound 1 with arylideneamino derivatives (7) in absolute ethanol in presence of sodium acetate afforded the hydrazones (8a-c), which on refluxing with ethanol containing a few drops of piperidine⁵, through cycloaddition reaction, led to the formation of 2-[2'-6'-chloropyrimidin-4'-yl]-3-aryl-3,4-dihydro-7-phenyl-5,6-dimethylpyrazolo[4,3-e][1,2,4]-triazines (9a-c), respectively.

Scheme 2

2-Amino-4-hydrazino-6-chloropyrimidine (1) was also condensed with isoxazole derivatives in aqueous ethanol to give the acid hydrazides (10a-c) which on boiling with aqueous 2N sodium

hydroxide⁶ led to the formation of 2-[2'-amino-6'-chloropyrimidin-4'-yl]-5-arylidene-3-phenyl-1,2,4-triazin-6(1*H*)-ones (11a—c), respectively. Moreover, condensation of compound 1 with 1-aryloxyindol-2,3-diones (12a—c) in absolute ethanol gave the hydrazones (13a—c), which underwent cyclocondensation on treatment with guanidine hydrochloride in sodium ethylate³ to yield 10-[2'-amino-6'-chloropyrimidin-4'-ylhydrazono]-4-aryl-2-imino-1,3,5-triazino-[1,2-*a*]indoles (14a—c) respectively. 1-Substituted-2*H*-3-methyl-1,2,4-benzotriazine (15) was isolated from refluxing of compound 1 with 2-methylbenzoxazole in dry pyridine⁷. Finally, the interaction of compound 1 with chloroacetamide in DMF⁸ gave 1,2-disubstituted-hydrazine (16) which on boiling with glacial acetic acid in presence of fused sodium acetate yielded 2-[2'-amino-6'-chloropyrimidin-4'-yl]-1,6-dihydro-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazin-5-one (17).

Uv spectra reveal that the $n-\pi^*$ transitions due to 1,2,4-triazine moiety are observed in the case of compounds 11 and 15, but these bands disappear in the case of molecule exhibiting steric inhibition of resonance (17).

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 293 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (DMF) on a Perkin-Elmer 550S spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a JNM PM X60 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The synthesis of compound 1 have been previously reported⁹. All the compounds were analysed for C, H, N and Cl and the results were found satisfactory.

The hydrazones (2a—c): An equimolar mixture of 2-amino-4-hydrazino-6-chloropyrimidine (1) and the appropriate acetophenone derivatives in ethanol was refluxed for 15 min, then cooled and the resulting solid was recrystallised from proper solvent to give the products: 2a (70%), m.p. 195–96°(EtOH); 2b (50%), 170–71° (MeOH); 2c (70%), 260–61° (DMF); 2a ν_{\max} 1 630–1 600 (C=C, C=N, δ NH₂ and NH) and 3 260–3 120 cm⁻¹ (NH and NH₂).

The substituted hydrazines (3a—c): A mixture of 2a—c (0.01 mol) and KCN (0.01 mol, in 10 ml H₂O) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) and ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, then cooled and diluted with cold water. The resulting solid was recrystallised from proper solvent: 3a (50%), m.p. 205–06° (EtOH); 3b (30%) 258–59° (EtOH); 3c (50%), 275–76° (DMF); 3a ν_{\max} 1 630–1 580 (C=C, C=N δ NH₂ and NH), 2 260 (C≡N) and 3 260–3 130 cm⁻¹ (NH and NH₂).

1,2,4-Triazino[4,3-*c*]pyrimidin-4-ones (4a—c): Compounds 3a—c (2 g) in concentrated HCl (50%, 5 ml) was refluxed for 4 h, then cooled and diluted with cold water. The resulting solid was crystallised from proper solvent: 4a (30%), m.p. > 300°

(EtOH); 4b (30%), 270–71° (EtOH); 4c (50%), > 300° (DMF); 4a ν_{\max} 1 640–1 600 (C=C, C=N, δ NH₂ and NH), 1 700 (C=O) and 3 250–3 100 cm⁻¹ (NH and NH₂); λ_{\max} 325 and 270 nm; δ 1.3 (3H, s, C₈–CH₃), 6.6 (2H, s, C₆–NH₂), 7.4 (5H, m, ArH and C₉–H) and 10.3 (1H, s, NH).

The hydrazone (5): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and 4-aminoantipyrine (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) and a few drops of acetic acid was refluxed for 1 h and then cooled to yield the product (30%), m.p. 120–21° (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1 650–1 600 (C=C, C=N, δ NH₂ and NH) and 3 400–3 200 cm⁻¹ (NH and NH₂).

Pyrazolo[4,3-*e*][1,2,4]triazine derivative (6): Compound 5 (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) with fused sodium acetate (10 g), was refluxed for 6 h, then cooled and diluted with cold water. The solid thus obtained was crystallised (50%), m.p. 260–61° (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1 650–1 630 (C=C, C=N and δ NH₂) and 3 265–3 180 cm⁻¹ (NH₂); δ 0.7, 1.8 and 2.1 (each 3H, s, CH₃), 6.7 (1H, s, C'₂–NH), 7.0–7.3 (6H, m, ArH and pyrimidine proton) and 8.3 (1H, s, NH).

The hydrazones (8a—c): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and Schiff base 7 (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) with fused sodium acetate (5 g), was refluxed for 2 h, then cooled and diluted with cold water. The resulting solid was crystallised from the proper solvent: 8a (65%), m.p. 250–51° (EtOH); 8b (70%), 260–61° (EtOH); 8c (60%), 170–71°(EtOH).

Pyrazolo[4,3-*e*][1,2,4]triazines (9a—c): Compounds 8a—c (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) with a few drops of piperidine, was refluxed for 8 h, then cooled and the formed solid was crystallised from proper solvent: 9a, b, c (60%), m.p. > 300 (DMF); 9c (50%), > 300° (DMF); 9a ν_{\max} 1 650–1 610 (C=C, C=N cyclic, δ NH₂ and NH) and 3 500–3 100 cm⁻¹ (NH and NH₂); λ_{\max} 355 (1,2,4-triazino) and 270 nm; δ 0.9 (3H, s, C₈–CH₃), 1.0 (3H, s, N–CH₃), 3.3 (1H, d, C₈–H) and 6.6–7.5 (13H, m, ArH, NH, NH₂ and pyrimidine proton).

The acid hydrazides (10a—c): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and the appropriate isoxazole derivative (0.01 mol) in aqueous ethanol (100 ml) and a few drops of acetic acid, was refluxed for 2 h, then cooled and the solid thus obtained was recrystallised from proper solvent: 10a (70%), m.p. 290–91° (EtOH); 10b (60%), 180–81° (EtOH); 10c (70%), 165–66° (EtOH); 10c ν_{\max} 1 630–1 580 (C=C, C=N, δ NH₂ and NH), 1 700 (C=O) and 3 500–3 100 cm⁻¹ (NH, NH₂ and OH).

2,3-Disubstituted-5-arylidene-1,2,4-triazin-6(1*H*)-ones (11a—c): A mixture of 10a—c (0.01 mol) and aqueous 2 *N* sodium hydroxide (100 ml) was refluxed for 4 h, then cooled and neutralised with dilute HCl. The resulting solid was recrystallised from the proper solvent: 11a (50%), m.p. > 300° (DMF); 11b, (30%), > 300° (EtOH); 11c (40%), > 300° (DMF);

11c, ν_{\max} 1 620 (C=C, C=N, δ NH₂ and NH), 1 700 (C=O and 3 550–3 100 cm⁻¹ (NH, NH₂ and OH); δ 1.7 (3H, s, CH₃) and 7.6 (14H, m, ArH, exocyclic =CH, NH, NH₂ and pyrimidine proton).

The hydrazones (13a–c): A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and 1-aryloxyindol-2,3-diones (**12a–c**; 0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) with fused sodium acetate (5 g), was refluxed for 1 h, then cooled and diluted with cold water. The resulting solid was crystallised from the proper solvent: **13a** (60%), m.p. 260–61° (EtOH); **13b** (50%), 270–71° (EtOH); **13c** (60%), 235–6° (EtOH); **13a** ν_{\max} 1 650–1 590 (C=C, C=N, δ NH₂ and NH), 1 750 (C=O) and 3 400–3 100 cm⁻¹ (NH and NH₂).

1,3,5-Triazino[1,2-a]indoles (14a–c): A mixture of **13a–c** (0.01 mol) and guanidine hydrochloride (0.01 mol, in 10 ml water) in sodium ethylate (0.5 g Na in 50 ml absolute ethanol) was, refluxed for 4 h then cooled and poured into ice-HCl. The resulting solid was crystallised from the proper solvent: **14a** (50%), m.p. 300° (DMF); **14b** (40%), > 300° (DMF); **14c** (40%), > 300° (DMF), **14a** ν_{\max} 1 650–1 610 (C=C, C=N, δ NH₂ and NH) and 3 400–3 220 cm⁻¹ (NH and NH₂); λ_{\max} 320 and 285 nm.

1-Substituted-2H-3-methyl-1,2,4-benzotriazine (15): An equimolar mixture of **1** and 2-methylbenzoxazole in dry pyridine (100 ml), was refluxed for 8 h, then cooled and poured into ice-concentrated HCl. The solid thus obtained was recrystallised (50%), m.p. > 300° (DMF); ν_{\max} 1 650–1 580 (C=C, C=N, δ NH₂ and NH) and 3 300–3 175 cm⁻¹ (NH and NH₂); ν_{\max} 435, 415 and 275 nm.

1,2-Disubstituted-hydrazine (16): A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and chloroacetamide (0.01 mol) in

DMF (50 ml) was refluxed for 1 h, then cooled and diluted with cold water. The resulting solid was recrystallised (30%), m.p. 226–27° (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1 630–1 600 (C=C, C=N, δ NH₂ and NH), 1 670 (C=O) and 3 300–3 200 cm⁻¹ (NH and NH₂).

2,3-Disubstituted-1,6-dihydro-1,2,4-triazin-5-one (17): A mixture of **16** (2 g) and glacial acetic acid (20 ml) with fused sodium acetate (5 g), was refluxed for 6 h, then cooled and poured into ice. The resulting solid was recrystallised (50%), m.p. 260–61° (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1 635–1 570 (C=C, C=N, δ NH₂ and NH), 1 675 (C=O) and 3 385–3 200 cm⁻¹ (NH and NH₂); λ_{\max} 285 nm; δ 1.9 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.6 (2H, d, CH₂CO) and 6.6 (4H, m, NH, NH₂ and pyrimidine proton).

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